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Alphonsus Orisaremi And Digital Lighting Technology In Nigerian Theatre

Emmanuel B. Akpieri & Martin U.E. Tugbokorwei (Ph.D)

Department of Theatre Arts, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This research examines the impact of digital lighting technology on Nigerian theatre, with particular focus on the work of Alphonsus Orisaremi, a pioneering theatre designer. It explores how digital lighting has transformed theatrical productions in Nigeria, enhancing the visual experience and enabling more dynamic, immersive performances. Through analysis of Orisaremi's innovative use of digital lighting, the study highlights the ways in which technology has influenced storytelling, atmosphere, and audience engagement in Nigerian theatre. By focusing on Orisaremi's contributions, the study offers insight into how digital lighting is reshaping the artistic and technical landscape of Nigerian theatre. Ultimately, the research underscores the potential of digital technologies in advancing the global visibility and artistic expression of African theatre. This study adopted the qualitative methodology to explore the integration of digital lighting technology in Nigerian theatre. The qualitative approach included interviews and content analysis.

Keywords: Digital, Lighting, Technology, Nigerian Theatre, Alphonsus Orisaremi

INTRODUCTION

Theatre is a world-wide phenomenon. By this we mean that theatre finds expression in Every culture or society in the world. This is irrespective of the culture or society's level of development or lack of it. In these different cultures and societies that make up the world, we also find expressed different kinds of theatrical art, or what some scholars would prefer to call performing or performance arts (Tugbokorwei, 2018, p. 169). Nigerian theatre has historically had a strong foundation in the oral traditions of dance-drama, music, and storytelling. Open-air venues were frequently used for performances, which relied on natural lighting or simple stagecraft. Due to the constraints of their era, early pioneers such as Hubert Ogunde, Kola Ogunmola, and Duro Ladipo gave cultural storytelling and thematic depth precedence above technical expertise.

However, the rise of contemporary theatre techniques has led to a greater focus on technical aspects like lighting, sound, and stage design. A worldwide breakthrough, digital lighting technology has brought cutting-edge instruments that enable stage shows to be more creative, flexible, and precise. Unlike conventional techniques, digital lighting systems give designers the ability to instantly adjust colours, lighting signals, and intensity to produce dynamic and engrossing visual experiences. These developments have established a standard for international theatre, which Nigerian plays strive to meet.

According to Orisaremi (2006), new methods and approaches to design continue to evolve all the time. In theatre design, there is a convergence of art and technology and the dynamic nature of the theatre allows for utilization of science and especially technological output there must have been a prior artistic input in the forms- of design as an integral part of planning. In Nigeria, the integration of digital lighting technology remains limited due to challenges such as the high cost of equipment, inadequate technical training, and poor infrastructural support. Despite these obstacles, figures like Alphonsus Orisaremi have made significant strides in promoting and utilizing digital lighting in Nigerian theatre.

Alphonsus Shereku Orisaremi is a Nigerian practitioner artist who specializes in the technical aspect of the theatre. Currently, he is a reader (Associate Professor) at the University of Ibadan, Oyo state Nigeria where he lectures and practice his own style when it comes to technical theatre using digital and automated lighting system. Orisaremi's work has been instrumental in pushing the boundaries of what is achievable in stage design and media, blending artistic creativity with technological innovation to deliver visually compelling productions.

This study is focused on examining how Alphonsus Orisami's work has contributed to bridging the gap on integrating modern technological advancement, like digital lighting, into traditional Nigerian Theatre. In doing this, this study aims at analyzing Alphonsus Orisami's contributions to modern lighting design in Nigerian Theatre through exploring the role of digital lighting in enhancing the visual aesthetics of Nigerian theatre.

This study adopted the qualitative methodology to explore the integration of digital lighting technology in Nigerian theatre. The qualitative approach will include:

Interviews: In-depth interviews with lighting designers, theatre practitioners, and industry experts to gather insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with digital lighting adoption.

Content Analysis: A detailed analysis of Alphonsus Orisaremi's works, examining his contributions to lighting design and their impact on the evolution of theatre technology in Nigeria. By focusing on qualitative methods, the research aims to provide a rich, contextual understanding of the subject, capturing the nuanced perspectives of stakeholders and the broader cultural implications of technological advancements in Nigerian theatre.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Historical Development of Lighting in Nigerian Theatre

Nigeria is a country renowned for its rich and diverse cultures, stemming from the multi-ethnic nationalities that comprise it. This diversity is evident in the nation's more than four hundred and seventy (470) tribes (Anyanwu 2019, p. 717). The evolution of Nigerian theatre is deeply interwoven with the country's cultural heritage, traditions, belief systems, and daily rituals. African theatre, by extension, is not merely an artistic expression but a reflection of communal life, spiritual beliefs, and historical narratives passed down through generations. Understanding the historical development of lighting in Nigerian theatre necessitates a broader exploration of the origins of professional theatre in the country, as well as the nature and role of African traditional theatre in shaping its growth.

Several scholars, including Austine Anigala, Joel Adedeji, Yemi Ogunbiyi, Jas Amankulor, and A.B.C. Duracle, have contributed significantly to the discourse on traditional African drama and its cultural underpinnings. Their insights provide a foundational understanding of how Nigerian theatre has evolved, particularly in terms of performance, stage design, and lighting.

Anigala (2005) defines traditional African drama as a form of dramatic composition that emerges within the context of festivals and their aesthetic principles. He asserts that traditional drama is intrinsically linked to the customs, religious beliefs, and artistic expressions of the community, which dictate the performance style and visual elements (p. 19). In traditional African theatre, lighting was predominantly natural, relying on sunlight for daytime performances and torches, lanterns, or fire-based sources for nighttime rituals and storytelling. This form of illumination was not merely functional but symbolic, representing spiritual presence, ancestral guidance, or the thematic undertones of the performance.

Ossai-Uloku and Anyanwu (2024) expanded on this idea, defining culture as a broad spectrum of human experiences, encompassing material, customs, ideas, emotions, behaviours, morality, and more. They add that culture represents the structured way of life of a particular group, serving as a key source of their identity (p. 183). This assertion aligns with the traditional use of lighting in Nigerian theatre, where fire and natural light played essential roles in creating ambience, directing focus, and enhancing the audience's emotional engagement with the performance.

Similarly, A.B.C. Duracle posits that traditional African drama consists of indigenous art forms that have remained untainted by modernisation over the years (pg). This perspective underscores the authenticity and originality of African theatre before external influences began reshaping its production elements. Traditional African theatre was largely performed in open spaces, village squares, or sacred groves, where lighting was dictated by nature or controlled through fire-lit sources.

These rudimentary lighting techniques not only illuminated the performance space but also heightened the mystical and ritualistic aspects of indigenous theatre.

Jas Amankulor reinforces this idea by asserting that traditional African drama remains "real" only when it has not been modernised or influenced by Western elements (p. 85). In other words, the essence of African theatre lies in its ability to retain its original aesthetic values, including its approach to lighting relying on sunlight for daytime performances and torches, lanterns, or fire-based sources for nighttime rituals and storytelling.

According to Oni (2004) in *Stage Lighting Design: The Nigerian Perspective*, "Stage lighting design in Nigeria, since 1880, has gone through several developmental stages. While it was initially aimed at only achieving general illumination, stage lighting design in contemporary Nigerian theatre is advancing to the stage of substantially reducing the use of stage sets... the required fluidity in the establishment of a tempo-spatial realisation has to rely significantly and inevitably on-stage lighting" (p. 85). Oni categorises the history of stage lighting into three distinct generations. The first spans from 1880 to 1944, tracing its origins to the courtyard Alarinjo travelling theatre. The second, covering 1945 to 1976, highlights the rise of the popular travelling theatre of the 1930s, with Hubert Ogunde as a key figure, and examines the effects of colonialism on Nigerian stage lighting. The third generation, from 1977 to the present, reflects the lasting impact of FESTAC '77 on Nigerian theatre (Oni, 2004, p. 86).

However, with the arrival of colonial influences and the eventual introduction of Western-style theatre, including Christianity, colonial rule, and the proscenium stage, Nigerian theatre began to adopt artificial techniques introduced by the colonial masters, including technical aspects of stage production. This was part of the broader process of civilisation in Africa. According to Yerima, the real contribution of colonialism was the provision of a model for the development of literary drama. In its origins and early development, literary drama bore little relation to traditional drama (p. 40).

According to Afolabi (2018), the historical development of stage lighting can be traced back to the Yoruba travelling theatre. The theatre had deep ritualistic connections to deities such as Sango, the divinity of thunder, whose reverence was performed through drama and theatre. Traditional performance modes have strongly influenced major figures in contemporary Nigerian theatre. The Alarinjo theatrical tradition sprang from the Egungun masquerade of Oyo Igboho (p. 19).

The Role of Hubert Ogunde in Modern Theatre Lighting

Hubert Ogunde (born 1916, Ososa, near Ijebu-Ode, Nigeria, died 4 April 1990, London, England) was a Nigerian playwright, actor, theatre manager, and musician, widely recognised as a pioneer in Nigerian folk opera, a dramatic form in which music and dancing play a significant role. He was the founder of the Ogunde Concert Party in 1945, the first professional theatrical company in Nigeria. Often regarded as the father of Nigerian theatre, Ogunde sought to reawaken interest in his country's indigenous culture while modernising its theatrical practices.

One of Ogunde's most significant contributions to Nigerian theatre was in the area of stage lighting. His theatre revolutionised the use of artificial lighting in performances, setting a precedent for future theatrical productions in Nigeria. Before his intervention, traditional theatre relied primarily on natural daylight or rudimentary fire-lit sources such as torches, lanterns, and bonfires. However, Ogunde recognised the need for controlled lighting to enhance stagecraft, create mood, and direct audience focus in a more structured manner. According to Duro Oni in his inaugural lecture at the University of Ibadan, Ogunde's quest for perfection led him to travel to England with his wife in 1947, where he spent £2,000 on lighting and stage equipment. Ogunde, as a showbiz impresario, was keenly aware of the role that stage lighting and equipment could play in theatre beyond illumination, and he fully explored this.

This marked a pivotal shift from the traditional reliance on natural and fire-lit sources to the incorporation of artificial lighting in Nigerian theatre. Upon returning to Nigeria, he integrated this equipment into his productions, enhancing the visual and atmospheric elements of his performances. His adoption of modern lighting techniques significantly improved audience engagement, allowing for better scene transitions, dramatic effects, and more immersive storytelling.

The Introduction of Digital Lighting to Nigerian Theatre

Over time, the world has experienced remarkable advancements in science, art, and technology. These three fields have continued to intersect, shaping the modern digital age in which we now live. Like many aspects of theatre, lighting has evolved through different stages, adapting to new trends and innovations. In recent years, Nigerian theatre has begun embracing digital lighting, marking a major departure from traditional illumination techniques.

In the 21st century, the widespread adoption of digital lighting technology, including innovations such as LED fixtures, programmable lighting consoles, and moving head lights, has significantly transformed the landscape of Nigerian theatre. These advanced tools offer unprecedented control over various aspects of lighting design, such as intensity, colour, timing, and movement, allowing designers to craft intricate and synchronised effects that were previously unattainable. By enhancing visual storytelling and creating immersive atmospheres, digital lighting technology has propelled Nigerian theatre to new heights of artistic expression and technical sophistication, bridging the gap between local productions and global standards of excellence.

According to Agha and Anyanwu, "modern lighting design has developed tremendously not just in technology and dynamics, but also in sophistication. These obvious developments, which are best experienced with automated lighting fixtures, offer functionalities that are far more user-friendly and significantly different from early theatre lanterns, which were better described as 'plug and play'" (p. 274). They further explain that although "the art of stage lighting design was the last design element to find its way into theatre, it has revolutionised theatre practice. This is evident in the range of aesthetics now possible in modern productions features that were not available in early theatre. Lighting design has continued to advance in sophistication, technique, and style. The increasing attention given to lighting design over the years is largely due to its crucial role in theatrical production" (p. 275).

The integration of science and art has strengthened over the years, particularly through advancements in computer science. Oni highlights that modern lighting designers now have access to tools that were once unavailable. These include computer-controlled intensity, movement, and colour adjustments, all of which reflect the rapid acceleration of technological change and its impact on theatre practice. Orisaremi supports this perspective, stating that "new methods and approaches to design continue to emerge over time. In theatre design, there is a convergence of art and technology, and the dynamic nature of theatre allows for the utilisation of science and technology in a composite form. This is because every scientific and technological innovation has an underlying artistic input in its design and planning" (Orisaremi2006).

Orisaremi further explained in details from his view, how digital lighting evolved in Nigeria: Most of the things in Nigeria came at the appropriate time. Using the screen as example, they first set of screens came into Nigeria in the early part of last century which were the big screen then came the small screen. But the screen gain relevance in the middle of last century too. Theatre arts as a field of study also started gaining prominence in the 60's e.g a field of study all over the world. This was because within the context theatre formal documentation started the theory and history of theatre arts was now being studied in institutions.

Digital light itself moved with the time; the system was analogue for a long time. As at the time I was a student in the 80s, in the University of Ibadan, we were privy to go into and other places, we now have path of digital and analogue dimmer so the digital lighting system started the controls. There were controls that were both digital and analogue and till today, they still exist in the theatre. So in the 80s there was already an invention that was both digital and analogue from strangle lighting. Then in the 90's, there was growth in the control system and then the emergence of digital lighting became prominent as lighting instrument. It started with the control system after which we started having digital lighting. Automated then came on board in the 90's and it started with the scanners. The scanners are designed with mirror reflectors, these mirror reflectors distribute the rays. The light ray is set into a reflector then the mirror reflector brings the ray to the computerized scanners which allows the lights to be scanned into the stage. These set of light were of more utilities to the musical concerts as at that time it was at that time.

Zmirage opened up in Nigeria in year 1997, the Compeered operation in Nigeria in 1998. This establishment gave birth to moving head lights on commercial scale in Nigeria in the 90's. These then

gave birth to change in current lighting when the world moved to L.E.D lights (Light Emitting Diodes) system. The light responds automatically to digital controls, it is also adaptable to computer control system. By 2000, there was a boom in digital lighting system in the Nigeria lighting culture. This observation emphasises that advancements in theatre lighting are not solely the products of science but also the result of artistic creativity and design. The evolution of lighting in Nigerian theatre has largely been driven by developments in computer science, making digital lighting an integral part of modern theatre productions.

About Alphonsus Orisaremi: A Biographical Sketch

Alphonsus Shereku Orisaremi (PhD) is a distinguished Nigerian theatre practitioner and scholar, widely recognised for his expertise in the technical aspects of theatre production, particularly in lighting design. An indigene of Edo State, Nigeria, he has made significant contributions to the advancement of stagecraft in the country through the integration of digital lighting technologies into theatrical practice.

Presently, Dr Orisaremi serves as a Reader (equivalent to Associate Professor) in the Department of Theatre Arts at the University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. In this role, he combines academic scholarship with practical application, pioneering a unique approach to technical theatre that harnesses the power of digital and automated lighting systems. His work continues to inspire a new generation of theatre professionals, bridging the gap between traditional methods and emerging technological trends.

Dr Orisaremi's academic journey began at the University of Ibadan, where he obtained his Bachelor of Arts degree in 1991. He proceeded to earn a Master of Arts degree in 1994, and later completed his Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in 2011, all from the same institution. His academic progression laid the foundation for his enduring commitment to excellence in the technical dimensions of theatre. After his postgraduate studies, Orisaremi sought to deepen his practical knowledge by enrolling at the National Theatre, Lagos, where he studied Professional Graphics. There, he received hands-on training in key areas such as light design, set design, and stage design, an experience that further strengthened his technical proficiency.

Plate 1: Dr. Alphonsus Shireku Orisaremi- source: Alphonsus Orisaremi Facebook Page

His professional breakthrough came when he joined the African Independent Television (AIT), Nigeria's first private television station, as the pioneer Lighting Director. At AIT, he was exposed to the modern dynamics of broadcast lighting and was introduced to the evolving field of digital lighting. This period marked a turning point in his career, as he transitioned from analogue systems to exploring the potentials of digital lighting technologies.

According to Orisaremi, in a personal interview, his deepened interest in digital lighting was significantly influenced by his late mentor, Chief Dr Raymond Dokpesi, the founder of AIT. Dokpesi sponsored his professional training at *Strand Lighting*, an internationally renowned lighting company based in Italy. During this training, which lasted several weeks, Orisaremi was taught advanced techniques in digital lighting control systems and installation procedures. Although the training was brief, it was intensive, and his prior grounding in analogue systems allowed him to quickly grasp and adapt to the principles of digital lighting.

Dr Orisaremi explained that the purpose of the training was not merely to learn the mechanics of the technology, but to "adopt, adapt, and imagine" new possibilities for lighting design in a digital world. This philosophical approach to technology, viewing it not as a replacement, but as an extension of traditional methods has remained central to his practice and teaching. Upon his return to Nigeria in the year 2000, he was invited by Professor Femi Osofisan, a renowned playwright and academic, to join the Department of Theatre Arts at the University of Ibadan as a lecturer. This marked the beginning of his formal teaching career, where he has since trained and mentored numerous students in the art and science of technical theatre.

Dr Orisaremi's teaching is heavily influenced by the strong technical theatre tradition that characterised the University of Ibadan during his student days. He frequently acknowledges the influence of his mentors, the late Dr Sunbo Marinho and Dr Olusola Aborisade, who coordinated the university's robust technical theatre unit. Their commitment to excellence and innovation deeply shaped Orisaremi's own philosophy and continues to reflect in his pedagogical and professional approach. Today, Dr Alphonsus Orisaremi stands as a leading voice in Nigerian theatre, particularly in the field of digital lighting technology. His blend of theoretical knowledge, professional experience, and creative innovation has contributed immensely to the modernisation of stage design and has elevated the standards of theatrical production in Nigeria and beyond.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Roles in the Adaptation and Integration of Digital Lighting

After undergoing an intensive professional training programme at *Strand Lighting* in Italy, Dr Alphonsus Orisaremi returned to Nigeria with a renewed commitment to modernising the technical practices in Nigerian theatre, particularly in the area of lighting. His experience abroad opened his eyes to the cutting-edge possibilities offered by digital lighting systems, and he immediately recognised the urgent need to upgrade and reposition local practices to match international standards. Armed with a strong foundation in analogue lighting systems, which he had mastered through years of practical engagement, Orisaremi did not aim to discard the traditional methods outright. Instead, he envisioned a creative integration of both analogue and digital techniques, an approach that would allow theatre practitioners and students alike to understand the past while embracing the future.

During his first week of training in Italy, his prior experience proved invaluable. Unlike someone encountering digital lighting technology for the first time, Orisaremi was already conversant with the fundamentals of light design. This gave him a significant advantage in adapting quickly to the new methods and tools being presented. At the time, *CorelDRAW* a widely used graphic design software was one of the primary tools for visual planning in lighting and stage design. Orisaremi recalled that he used *CorelDRAW* to create his very first computer-aided lighting design. This design, developed during his training, would later serve as the foundational plan for the lighting setup of the AIT (African Independent Television) studio in Nigeria, where he had previously worked as the pioneer Lighting Director. This milestone was more than a personal achievement; it marked the beginning of a paradigm shift in his approach to theatrical lighting. By merging computer-aided design software with the practical demands of live performance, Orisaremi began to formulate a hybrid model that balanced precision, artistry, and modern technology.

Following his return to Nigeria in the year 2000, Orisaremi was invited to join the Department of Theatre Arts at the University of Ibadan as an Assistant Lecturer. With the insights gained from his international training, he was determined to transform the way lighting and set design were taught and practised in academic settings. His first priority was to build upon the legacy of his mentors Dr Sunbo Marinho and Dr Olusola Aborisade who had laid the groundwork for technical theatre education at the university. Picking up where they had left off, he began to introduce his students to the fundamentals of digital lighting, computer-generated design, and automated lighting systems. This move signaled a dramatic shift in the curriculum and in the practical exposure available to students. Traditionally, theatre students were trained primarily with analogue tools, learning to operate manually controlled lighting rigs, gel filters, and basic switchboards. However, with Orisaremi's intervention, they began to engage with digital lighting consoles, intelligent fixtures, software-based designs, and pre-visualization techniques that allowed for more dynamic and expressive stage environments.

Unlike lighting setups used for television presenters or musical performances, where lights are often static or repetitive Orisaremi emphasised lighting that was responsive to the live theatrical form. In theatre, he explained, lighting must follow the story; it must adapt to character movement, mood changes, and the dramatic arc of the performance. His teaching prepared students to think of lighting not as a background element, but as an active and intentional part of the performance. In a personal conversation, Orisaremi shared his reflections on the importance of this transition:

The moment I arrived in the University of Ibadan; I understood the essence of upgrade in the theatre. I continued from where my mentors stopped (my teachers) back then in school. After that I introduced the students to the art and science of digital lights and set designs.

His approach was not dismissive of the past. On the contrary, he consistently emphasised the importance of understanding and appreciating the analogue systems that had served Nigerian theatre for decades. He was keen to highlight that while technology evolves, the value of foundational knowledge remains intact. He explained:

In order to appreciate the use of analog lights as at then; let us not make any mistake, the analogue theatre which our teachers taught us was what was obtainable as at that time and it was very very relevant for its own time and period. But when I came in, the digital light was starting and I was fortunate to have worked with AIT because I didn't just graduate from the university, I did my masters and I picked up employment. The AIT gave me the opportunity to introduce the digital lighting and set designs to the student and to the theatre community especially in the educational settings.

In 2000, Dr. Alphonsus Orisaremi introduced students to digital lighting and set design, pioneering its teaching at the University of Ibadan. Utilizing his personal laboratory, he meticulously imparted the intricate art and scientific principles of digital lighting. Notably, the university lacked its own digital lighting infrastructure, prompting Orisaremi to establish his laboratory just opposite the university's second gate in Ojo, Ibadan, Oyo State. Orisaremi explained this in details in an interview when asked how he was able to initiate the use of Digital lights to the theatre in the University of Ibadan. He replied:

When I came to the University of Ibadan in Year 2000, the entire system has never experience digital lighting system. It was I that revolutionized the use of digital lighting system. The Department of Theatre Arts, University of Ibadan. I changed the system to digital lighting first, by inviting Zmirage to the system on working and other training. And then, I started a laboratory I used to train students who specialized in theatre designs technology in the University of Ibadan. By the time they graduate, they are already equipped with the knowledge of digital lighting system. Presently, there has never been a production in the department without the use of digital lighting in the last five sessions. 70% of the lights used are LED lights. I was able to attract some company like M.T.N to donate lights which were used in training the students. These exposed the student to lighting especially the Led lights and they make use of it in their productions. As a matter of fact, over the last ten years, the lighting system that has been used by students are digital lights which respond to computer commands. Most universities in Nigeria don't have the training opportunities, but it has begun starting from Dennis Osadebe University (DOU) Asaba where the students were exposed to digital lighting training. They are gradually getting used digital lights even though they are still learning.

This dedicated space not only served as a training ground for students but also operated as a commercial venture. Equipped with a warehouse for storing essential equipment, it ensured continual upkeep and maintenance of the laboratory. From 2000 to 2005, Orisaremi imported lighting technology from abroad, significantly advancing theatrical development within Nigeria.

Plate 2: Dr Alphoncus Orisaremi in his teaching process training students of the University of Ibadan 2018- source: Alphoncus Orisaremi Facebook Page

Through his visionary efforts, Dr Orisaremi has not only transformed the teaching and practice of technical theatre in Nigeria, but he has also ensured that future generations of theatre professionals are equipped to navigate an increasingly digital world. His work represents a rare fusion of tradition and innovation preserving the lessons of the past while preparing students for the challenges and opportunities of the future. His influence continues to resonate within academic institutions and professional theatre spaces alike, setting a new benchmark for what is possible in Nigerian stagecraft.

**Review of the African Independent Television (AIT) Digital Lighting Project:
Approaches to Studio/Theatre Lighting Design and Installation**

The African Independent Television (AIT) digital lighting project, as documented by Alphonus Orisaremi in his 2009 paper, stands out as a major step forward in Nigeria's theatre and studio lighting scene. This project didn't just bring modern equipment into a broadcasting studio; it redefined how lighting design and installation could be approached in a Nigerian context, blending artistic creativity with technical know-how in a way that was both innovative and deeply rooted in practical realities.

Lighting plays a crucial role in both theatre and television. It doesn't only make things visible, it helps to create mood, set the atmosphere, and guide the audience's focus. Orisaremi understood this perfectly. He saw lighting not just as a background tool, but as an essential storytelling element. He argued that a successful lighting designer must think like an artist while also being technically grounded, especially in a country like Nigeria, where infrastructure challenges and limited technical resources often complicate things.

Designing with Technology in Mind

One of the key points Orisaremi raised is that theatre and TV studios share more similarities than we often think. Both require lighting systems that can support different moods, performance styles, and production demands. He advocated for theatre training to include exposure to digital design tools and technical installation processes, especially the use of Computer-Aided Design (CAD). CAD software allows lighting designers to visualise how their concepts will work in real space and ensures clarity when communicating with architects, engineers, and other technical professionals.

AIT Studio architectural designs with digital lights in the interior- Source: Orisaremi (2005, p.109)

In the AIT project, this technology played a vital role. Working with Strand Lighting Italia, Orisaremi used CAD drawings and a detailed CD-ROM containing specifications for lighting instruments to create a practical and visually effective lighting plan. His design wasn't just a creative exercise it was a precise, technical blueprint that helped guide every stage of the installation.

AIT studio with digital lights installed- Source: Orisaremi (2005, p.109)

The Role of the Designer-Technologist

A particularly important idea Orisaremi discussed is the concept of the “designer-technologist”, someone who isn’t just creative but is also hands-on with the technical aspects of implementation. In other words, this person is both artist and engineer. In many Nigerian studios and theatres, the absence of properly trained technical staff means that the designer often has to step in and handle tasks that would typically be shared among several specialists. Orisaremi himself played this role during the AIT project. He designed the system, helped source and adapt equipment from overseas, and supervised the on-site installation from start to finish.

The speed and efficiency with which the AIT lighting system was delivered in just six weeks from design to completion show how important this designer-technologist role is. It bridges the gap between creative vision and practical execution, especially in environments where resources and time are tight.

Collaborating Across Disciplines

Another thing that made the AIT project work was effective collaboration between different professionals. Orisaremi didn’t work in isolation; he consulted with architects, engineers, and AIT’s own technical team to make sure everything fit together smoothly. For instance, during the building’s construction, he and the structural engineers worked out how to embed strong iron supports into the concrete ceiling. These would later hold up the studio’s fixed aluminum lighting grid, an important structure that allowed the lights to be properly mounted and adjusted. These kinds of collaborative decisions show how theatre and studio spaces are more successful when lighting designers are involved early in the process, rather than being brought in at the last minute. Orisaremi made it clear that designing a performance space isn’t just about architecture or aesthetics it’s about making sure every part of the space works together to support the production.

Functional Lighting Design

AIT’s studio had two main functional areas: one for news broadcasting and the other for general programming. The lighting setup had to reflect those needs. The news studio required a setup that was soft, flexible, and always ready to go so soft lights were chosen for their ability to give a clean, balanced look without harsh shadows. The general programming studio needed something more

adaptable, so it was equipped to handle a wider variety of lighting moods and angles. Orisaremi also made safety and functionality top priorities. He ensured that every lighting point had its own dedicated cable, reducing the risk of overloading or short circuits. Each cable was properly rated and insulated, and an effective earthing system was installed to protect both the crew and the building. This level of detail shows how much thought went into not just making the lighting look good, but also making it safe and sustainable in the long term.

Installation as a Creative Process

One of the most insightful parts of Orisaremi's work is how he talks about the installation process. For him, installation isn't just about fixing lights in place, it's an extension of the design process itself. Sometimes things don't go exactly as planned on paper, so a good designer must be able to adapt on site. This means knowing how to tweak designs, adjust positions, or even rethink parts of the plan in response to the actual space. At AIT, this was very much the case. The lighting grid had to be adjusted based on ceiling height and structural realities. Lights had to be positioned in a way that avoided shadows, balanced visual needs with technical limits, and aligned with camera setups. Orisaremi's hands-on approach made sure that the final setup wasn't just technically correct, but also artistically effective.

Lessons for Theatre Education and Practice

Apart from the immediate success of the AIT project, Orisaremi's work offers lasting value for theatre education in Nigeria. He strongly believes that students of theatre shouldn't be limited to performance and script analysis they also need to understand how lighting, sound, and digital tools work. His involvement in upgrading the lighting system at the University of Ibadan's Arts Theatre became a learning opportunity for students, who were invited to help with the actual installation. This gave them real-world experience that's hard to get in a typical classroom setting. Yet, despite all these efforts, Orisaremi was honest about the obstacles he faced. Getting approvals, sourcing equipment, and navigating bureaucracy were all major challenges. He described how difficult it was to convince decision-makers to invest in modern lighting technology, even when it was clearly needed. This reflects a wider problem in Nigeria's creative and academic institutions, one where innovation is often slowed down by outdated systems and lack of support.

The AIT digital lighting project is more than just a story about installing some lights. It's an example of what happens when creativity meets technical expertise in a well-coordinated, forward-thinking way. Orisaremi's work shows how important it is to have designers who are also skilled technicians, and to foster collaboration between different professionals when building performance spaces. His approach provides a model that other Nigerian studios, theatres, and institutions can follow. It also reinforces the need for better technical training in our theatre programmes, so that students come out prepared not just to act or direct, but to lead in areas like lighting, sound, and production technology. In a time when digital tools are reshaping performance everywhere, Nigeria must rise to the challenge, not by copying foreign models, but by building systems that suit our own environments. The AIT project offers a clear, practical example of how that can be done.

CONCLUSION

This study comes to the conclusion that digital lighting technology has enormous potential to transform stagecraft and improve artistic expression, even though it is still in its infancy as a component of Nigerian theatre. The initiatives of people like Alphonsus Orisaremi show that Nigerian practitioners may implement and even innovate in the field of digital lighting if they have the necessary expertise and vision. However, obstacles relating to infrastructure, education, finances, and legislation are impeding the shift from analog to digital. The majority of theatre settings in Nigeria would not fully benefit from digital lighting unless intentional institutional and governmental efforts are made.

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